

NEWS

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Welcome to our updated Newsletter

Many things are cooking and so we decided it is time for a new design of our Newsletter. We share way more content now, but made it more interactive so that you will be forwarded to the respective project sites and the original source of information. Enjoy reading this improved May edition of the E-VOLVE Cluster newsletter!

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All about Results: Reports, Publications & More

Disseminating project results is at the essence of our cluster projects and we are happy to support their outreach. Head over to our second page to find the most recent deliverables, publications and activities.

Past Project Activities

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Upcoming Meetings and Conferences

All about: Results

The RHODaS project is working on solutions to increase the stake of heavy-duty electric vehicles in road transport and has recently published two public deliverables:

- [Results Power Converters](#) (D2.4)
- [Lab Testing and Validation of the Thermal Management System](#) (D3.3)

HighScope, delivering high efficiency, high power density, cost effective, scalable and modular power electronics and control solutions for EVs published the report [Simulation models of the High-Scope vehicles, PE systems and components](#) (D2.3)

EFFEREST conducted an interview study on how EV drivers are balancing range and comfort and is sharing the valuable results on the [project website](#).

From the project HiPE, developing a new family of highly energy efficient, cost-effective, modular, compact and integrated wide bandgap power electronics solutions for the next generation of battery electric vehicles, you can read recent findings on thermal management, published in Power Systems Design:

- [Evaluating Next-Gen Power Packaging: How Top-Side Cooling Performs](#)

The proceedings from the TRA 2024 are available and many E-VOLVE Cluster projects were present including a joint paper [“E-VOLVE Cluster: Increasing Innovation Efficiency to Support the Transition Toward Sustainable e-mobility”](#) jointly prepared by the projects [HiPE](#), [HighScope](#), [RHODaS](#), [SCAPE](#), [EM-TECH](#) and [Multi-Moby](#).

Project & Cluster Activities

General Assembly

The logo for HiPE (Hydrogen Innovation Project Europe) features the word "HiPE" in a bold, sans-serif font. Above the "i" is a stylized green arc with a small green dot above it, resembling a leaf or a drop.

From May 7th to May 8th the project partners from HiPE came together for the fifth General Assembly in Istanbul at the premises of the partner Ford Otosan. [Click here to get some insights from the meeting!](#)

Working Group Industrialization & Exploitation

The working group Industrialization and Exploitation aims to support tangible exploitation targets and pathways for exploitation, while considering uncertainties related to industrialization / commercialization, as well as end of the respective R&D project and new setups. Read an update of the WG activities on our [website](#).

SAE World Congress

The E-VOLVE Cluster projects joined together and wrote two papers for the SAE World Conference in Detroit, USA, to share some insights on the latest e-mobility research in Europe. Represented were the projects [EFFEREST](#), [HEFT](#), [EM-TECH](#), [VOLT CAR](#), [MAXIMA](#), [SmartCorners](#), [MINDED](#) and [ClimaFlux](#). Find out more, by clicking [on this link](#).

RTR Conference

For the E-VOLVE Cluster projects [EM-TECH](#), [SCAPE](#), [MAXIMA](#), [VOLT CAR](#), [ClimaFlux](#) and [HEFT](#) it was time to present their activities at the [RTR Conference](#) in February 2025. All about the event on our [blog post!](#)

Upcoming Meetings and Conferences

General Assemblies		Conferences
 15.6.-18.6.2025 Gothenburg, Sweden		
 30.9.-1.10.2025 Brussels, Belgium		

The E-VOLVE Cluster Evolution

From the Achilles project, starting the E-VOLVE Cluster together with the founding projects in 2018, we are expressing our thanks to all project partners and projects contributing with their expertise to the European R&D landscape and collaborating in the E-VOLVE cluster.

